

Redes Generativas Adversarias en tiempos de posverdad:

**Avances, falacias, promesas y amenazas
en torno del cambio climático y el calentamiento global**

(Cambio climático e Inteligencia Artificial)

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Propósitos generales

- Analizar las principales etapas, corrientes y herramientas de la Inteligencia Artificial.
- Introducir el modelo de Redes Generativas Adversarias (GAN) y la técnicas de *deep learning*.
- Mostrar que el modelo de la posverdad es intrínseco a las GAN
- Las GAN como infraestructura necesaria de las *fake news* y otras variantes de *deep fakes*.
- Ilustrar modelos de GAN aplicados al modelado del cambio climático.
- Ejemplificar las perspectivas que se abren y las amenazas que se ciernen.

Agenda puntual

- Introducción a la Inteligencia Artificial
- Redes Neuronales Profundas y Aprendizaje Profundo
- Redes convolucionales profundas (CNN)
- Introducción a las Redes Generativas Adversarias (GAN)
- Introducción a la Posverdad: *Deep fakes*
- GAN y Cambio Climático
- Demo de ThisClimateDoesNotExist
- Conclusiones: Promesas y Amenazas
- Cómo seguir y qué hacer ahora
- Recursos sugeridos

Inteligencia Artificial

- Modelo lógico
 - Programa japonés de quinta generación
 - Programación lógica (LISP, Prolog)
 - Demostración de teoremas
 - Sistemas expertos
- Modelo de las redes neuronales
 - Perceptrones, Adalines
 - Redes neuronales [Artificiales]
 - Conexionismo
 - Redes Neuronales Profundas (DNN) – *Deep Learning*
 - Redes convolucionales (CNN)
 - Redes Generativas Adversarias (GAN)

Recurso para programación lógica en ciencias sociales

- [\(4\) Antropología y programación lógica \(Inteligencia artificial\) \(1991\) | Carlos Reynoso - Academia.edu](https://www.academia.edu/53296238/Antropología_y_programación_lógica_Inteligencia_artificial_(1991))

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL https://www.academia.edu/53296238/Antropología_y_programación_lógica_Inteligencia_artificial.... The page displays the profile of Carlos Reynoso, a Faculty Member at the Universidad de Buenos Aires. The main content is the title of his work, "Antropología y programación lógica (Inteligencia artificial) (1991)", which is his first doctoral dissertation from FFyL - UBA (481 pages). The page also shows statistics: 130 visualizations, 481 pages, and 2 archives. A list of tags includes Prolog, Antropología, Inteligencia Artificial, Conexionismo, and Redes Neuronales. Below the title, there are three buttons: "Descargar PDF", "Descargar Paquete PDF", and "Traducir PDF". At the bottom, there are three tabs: "PDF Original", "Resumen", and "Relacionado". On the right side, there is a section titled "ACERCA DEL AUTOR" with a profile picture of Carlos Reynoso and his credentials. Below this, there are statistics for "PUBLICACIONES" (213) and "SEGUIDORES" (1.372). A "READERS" section lists three people who read the work: Alejandro López (Investigador Adjunto, National Scientific and Technical Research Council, Argentina), andres felipe lopez gomez (Colombia), and Manuel Aguilar (Spain).

Recursos para tipología de redes neuronales (1940-1990)

- [\(3\) Ciencia Cognitiva y Antropología del Conocimiento - 15: Redes neuronales | Carlos Reynoso - Academia.edu](#)

Todo lo que siempre quiso saber sobre

Redes neuronales

y nunca se atrevió a preguntar

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Deep learning, redes
convolucionales y GAN

Redes generativas adversarias (GAN)

- Ian Goodfellow
 - Google Brain, Apple, Open AI, Deep Mind
 - PhD Universidad de Montréal (Yoshua Bengio, Aaron Courville)
 - Goodfellow, Ian J.; Pouget-Abadie, Jean; Mirza, Mehdi; Xu, Bing; Warde-Farley, David; Ozair, Sherjil; Courville, Aaron; Bengio, Yoshua (2014). "Generative Adversarial Networks".
[arXiv:1406.2661](https://arxiv.org/abs/1406.2661)
 - Código (Pyton) en [GitHub - goodfeli/adversarial: Code and hyperparameters for the paper "Generative Adversarial Networks"](https://github.com/goodfeli/adversarial)

GAN y *deep learning*

- Ian Goodfellow, Yoshua Bengio y Aaron Courville. *Deep learning*. Cambridge (USA), The MIT Press, 2016.

Redes generativas convolucionales

20 Deep Generative Models	645
20.1 Boltzmann Machines	645
20.2 Restricted Boltzmann Machines	647
20.3 Deep Belief Networks	651
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20.6 Convolutional Boltzmann Machines	673
20.7 Boltzmann Machines for Structured or Sequential Outputs	675
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20.14 Evaluating Generative Models	707
20.15 Conclusion	710

Redes Generativas Antagónicas

- “generative adversarial networks schema”

Rommetveit - Post-Truth Imagin: x G generative adversarial networks: x +

https://www.google.com/search?q=generative+adversarial+networks+schema&xsrf=APwXEdcV0D

Hotmail Academia LibGen Sci-Hub Patagonia Yahoo Nacion Trends Arqueomus AI Etnogeometria Giros Dialectics Otros favoritos

Google generative adversarial networks schema

machine learning wasserstein conditional flow discriminator neural tabular data gan architecture

Google Developers
GAN Structure | Machine Learning ...

ResearchGate
generative adversarial network (GAN ...

ResearchGate
Generative Adversarial Network (GAN ...

Toptal
Generative Adversarial Networks: Create ...

The Artificial Intelligence Wiki - Pathmind
A Beginner's Guide to Generative AI ...

The Artificial Intelligence Wiki - Pathmind
A Beginner's Guide to Generative AI ...

ResearchGate
Generative Adversarial Networks ...

Generative Adversarial Network

Random Input Vector
Generator

Generator $G(z, \theta_g)$
Noise z

$x \sim P_{data}$
Sampling of real observations

$P_{data} = \delta$ -subset of w using $\mathcal{L}(w, \theta_g, \theta_d) + \mathcal{L}_D$

GAN

Estructura antagónica del modelo, ligada a la dialéctica

- “[Existe] un nexo algorítmico tenue pero precisable entre la filosofía dialéctica [de Hegel y Marx] y las matemáticas de las funciones recursivas que componen el fundamento de las primitivas que componen las ciencias de la complejidad , el pensamiento complejo y sus ideas aledañas: retroalimentaciones de Wiener, *feedforward loops* y causalidades circulares de von Foerster, esquismogénesis de Bateson, *loops* de Hofstadter, [funciones] recursivas primitivas de Gödel, motivos de Escher, *ricercari* y *ritornelli* de Bach, histéresis de Maxwell, eternos retornos de Eliade, modelos [dialécticos] de Riemann y Lautman, funciones logísticas de Verhulst, bucles de Edgar Morin y *last but not least* convoluciones de las redes adversarias generativas, la última palabra en Inteligencia Artificial [...]. A quien pretenda cancelar e invitar a la abstención de todo rastro de primitivas dialécticas, ciclo temporal o idea afín, le advierto que es mucha ciencia y mucha tecnología la que deberá dejar al margen” (Reynoso 2023: 43, [en línea](#)).
- La idea ha sido más y mejor trabajada en la literatura , la filosofías y las ciencias sociales que en las ciencias “duras”.

Posverdad

Posverdad, redes generativas adversarias y cambio climático

- [Kjetil Rommetveit](#), 2022
- Paralelos entre la posverdad y la tecnociencia de las GAN
- La “palabra del año”:
 - 2016: “pos-verdad”
 - 2019: “emergencia climática”
 - 2023: “inteligencia artificial”
- GAN: surgen en 2014, con un *paper* conjunto de Ian Goodfellow y Yoshua Bengio
- *Deep learning*: Goodfellow, Bengio y otros

Posverdad, redes generativas adversarias y cambio climático

- Michael Filimowicz, 2022
- Particularmente datos sobre el primer video de Trump y capítulo sobre *deep fakes* en Asia
- Capítulo de Eunsong Kim “On the depth of the fakeness”

GAN en *deep fakes*

- Partido Socialista Sueco sube [video de Donald Trump](#) hablando en contra de la idea del cambio climático (2018)
- Técnicas de *deep fake impersonators* en el cine pornográfico
 - FakeApp, DeepFace Lab, Descript, Respeecher
- Uso de avatares o “anchors” en noticieros chinos en [Xinhua](#), inicialmente poco sofisticados (comparados con CGI)
- Desarrollo en paralelo de ChatGPT y GAN
- Uso de avatares basados en GAN en falso noticiero venezolano ([House of News](#), enero de 2023)
 - Denunciados en diario *El País* – Fuera de línea por reclamo de Synthesia
- [Fotografías](#) de Donald Trump siendo arrestado (abril 2023)
- Apocalípticos reclamando suspensión de la investigación y desarrollo en Inteligencia Artificial
 - [Elon Musk](#) vs [Bill Gates](#): ChatGPT y GANs en la picota
 - Investigación en modelos inteligentes de cambio climático, *idem*

Avatar - Fake persons by Synthesisia

- <https://share.synthesia.io/041a5484-284d-4d27-a9f3-19db7bcdac75>

synthesia

Hello"! This video is a demo of Synthesia Software in order to learn about using avatars. It was created by Carlos for the Second Congress of Climate Change at La Guajira, Colombia

Buscar

20:40
5/4/2023

Posibilidades de la convolución

Nvidia: El arte de CycleGAN

- [ThisPersonDoesNotExist](#)
- [ThisCityDoesNotExist](#)
- [ThisMountainDoesNotExist](#) (búsqueda por imágenes)
- [ThisBeachDoesNotExist](#) (idem)
- [ThisModelDoesNotExist](#)
- [ThisStreetViewDoesNotExist](#)
- [ThisXDoesNotExist](#)
- [ThisClimateDoesNotExist](#)

Gregory Bateson

- La cantidad no es una pauta
- La medida sí lo es
- Pasaje del modelo de similitud y diferencia de cantidad (Kolmogorov/Chaitin) a un modelo relacional más gestáltico y elástico
- Cuantitativo Cualitativo
- Las redes neuronales aprendieron a abstraer patrones
- Contrario a las predicciones de Hubert Dreyfus
 - *What computers can't do*
- Similitud y diferencia como pautas

Image-to-image translation

- Arun Solanki, Anand Nayyar y Mohd Naved, 2021
 - Referencias de galerías de imágenes
 - *Idem* estrategias basadas en GAN
 - P.ej. texto-imagen, Age-cGAN, CycleGAN para cambio estacional, etc

Image-to-Image translation (StarGAN V2)

Image-to-Image translation (CycleGAN)

Monet ↔ Photos

Zebras ↔ Horses

Summer ↔ Winter

Monet → photo

zebra → horse

summer → winter

photo → Monet

horse → zebra

winter → summer

Photograph

Monet

Van Gogh

Cezanne

Ukiyo-e

Aplicaciones gráficas poco explotadas en modelos de cambio climático

- Explorar, por ejemplo, párrafos de mi hipertexto como el siguiente:
 - “En lo que hace nada más que a aplicaciones generativas de creación artística, tenemos (por orden alfabético) a [AIPainter](#), [Artbreeder](#), [Artisto](#), [DALL-E2](#), [Deepdream Generator](#), [GANBreeder](#), [Midjourney](#), [Neuralstyle.art](#), [NightCafe Creator](#) (incluye algoritmos de [Stable diffusion](#), [DALL-E 2](#), [CLIP-Guided Diffusion](#) [demo], [VQGAN+CLIP](#) y [Neural Style Transfer](#)), [Pikazo](#), [Prisma](#), [RunwayML](#), [StyleMyPic](#), [Urza's AI](#) y [X Degrees of Separation](#). Si siguen una a una la huella de los vínculos podrán hacerse una idea. Sugiero desarrollar prestaciones de conversiones de texto a imagen en base a nociones que sugieran catástrofes ambientales o condiciones meteorológicas relacionadas con el cambio climático.”
- Recomiendo comenzar con [Stable diffusion](#).
- A veces no es necesario comenzar con gráficos y es suficiente una frase escrita o hablada.

Reconocimiento (gestáltico) de rostros

- Pawan Sinha: Ineficiencia del método por piezas tradicional (método analítico)

- Identikits de Bill Cosby, Tom Cruise, Ronald Reagan y Michael Jordan
- Imposible reconocer la similitud de una caricatura o una estilización

Reconocimiento (gestáltico) de rostros

- Y a la inversa, eficiencia del reconocimiento humano aún en casos de ruido

- Habitualmente muchos pueden reconocer al Rey Carlos, Woody Allen, Bill Clinton, Saddam Hussein, Richard Nixon y Ladi Di
- Inmensa importancia estratégica del reconocimiento automático.

Reconocimiento de patrones

- <https://lancaster.crimewatchpa.com/lbop/19659/arrests/nguyen-hung-phuoc-theft-unlawful-taking-2-counts>

NGUYEN, HUNG PHUOC – 2 COUNTS THEFT BY UNLAWFUL TAKING (M2)

FEBRUARY 7, 2018

WARRANT DETAILS

Warrant Location

*****ORIGINAL INFORMATION RELEASED 2/6/2018*****

THEFT

18-003278

THEFT

CENTRAL MARKET

OCCURRED 1/30/2018 1320 HRS.

Off. Rothermel took a report that an unknown male pretended to be an employee at a stand inside Central Market when an employee was away from the stand. The male took cash from the business and left the area on foot. The suspect was described as a male 30-40 years of age, 5'04" tall, petite build and was possibly South American or Asian. The suspect was further described as having straight, black hair that covered his ears and that he had wide-set cheekbones and a pointed chin. A witness provided Off. Rothermel with a hand-drawn sketch of the suspect. Anyone with information on this incident or the identity of the suspect is asked to contact Lancaster Police at [717-735-3300](tel:717-735-3300). Anonymous tips can also be submitted through this Crime watch page.

OFFENDER DETAILS

Media General Description

Reconocimiento de patrones

- <http://www.insideedition.com/cops-identify-hung-phuoc-nguyen-theft-suspect-despite-widely-mocked-sketch-40551>

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EDITION

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Couple Hilariously Shoots Engagement Photos at Target Because They Love it so Much

'Black Panther' Earns \$1 Billion at Worldwide Box Office

Cops Identify Hung Phuoc Nguyen as Theft Suspect, Despite Widely Mocked Sketch

CRIME 10:52 AM PST, February 8, 2018 - CAITLIN NOLAN

Vaya, no se pue mostrar esta pá

Prueba esto

- Asegúrate de que tie la dirección web corr <https://cas.us.criteo.c>

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Call Us: (212) 817-5555

TRENDING NOW

1. The Real Story Behind 'Three Billboards Outside Ebbing, Missouri'
2. Wild Otter Attacks 77-Year-Old Woman Kayaking on Florida River

Lancaster City PD

A sketch of a suspected thief that had generated laughs as little more than a cute doodle has actually led authorities in Pennsylvania to identify the man believed to be

Datasets

Datasets

[Fei Fei Li](#) – Machine learning, Deep learning, Cognitive neuroscience – ImageNet, 2006

A screenshot of a Google search for "imagenet database". The search results show several links to datasets and papers. The top result is "ImageNet Dataset | Papers With Code". Below it are "Devopedia ImageNet" and "Datasets - Activeloop ImageNet Dataset | Machine Learning ...". The right side of the screenshot shows a "Papers With Code" card for "ImageNet Dataset | Papers With Code" with a large grid of 1,000 x 1,000 images. The bottom left corner shows the URL "https://paperswithcode.com/dataset/imagenet".

Google imagenet database

Papers With Code
ImageNet Dataset | Papers With Co...

Devopedia
ImageNet

Datasets - Activeloop
ImageNet Dataset | Machine Learning ...

ResearchGate
7: Examples in the ImageNet dataset ...

A "Papers With Code" card for the "ImageNet Dataset". It features a large grid of 1,000 x 1,000 images. Below the grid is a "Visit" button and a link to "Learn More". The text "Images may be subject to copyright. Learn More" is also present.

Papers With Code

1,000 x 1,000

ImageNet Dataset | Papers With Code

Visit

Images may be subject to copyright. [Learn More](#)

<https://paperswithcode.com/dataset/imagenet>

Datasets

- <https://paperswithcode.com/datasets>

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the 'Datasets' page on Paperswithcode.com. The browser's address bar shows the URL 'https://paperswithcode.com/datasets'. The page features a blue header with a search bar, navigation links for 'Browse State-of-the-Art', 'Datasets', 'Methods', and 'More', and social media icons for Twitter and GitHub. Below the header, the text 'Datasets' is prominently displayed, followed by '8,038 machine learning datasets'. A notification bell icon with the text 'Share your dataset with the ML community!' is visible. The main content area shows '8038 dataset results' and a list of datasets. The first three results are:

- CIFAR-10**: The CIFAR-10 dataset (Canadian Institute for Advanced Research, 10 classes) is a subset of the Tiny Images dataset and consists of 60000 32x32 color images. The images are labelled with... 11,028 PAPERS • 69 BENCHMARKS
- ImageNet**: The ImageNet dataset contains 14,197,122 annotated images according to the WordNet hierarchy. Since 2010 the dataset is used in the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge... 10,631 PAPERS • 103 BENCHMARKS
- COCO (Microsoft Common Objects in Context)**: The MS COCO (Microsoft Common Objects in Context) dataset is a large-scale object detection...

On the left side of the page, there is a search filter section with a search bar labeled 'Search for datasets' and a dropdown menu set to 'Best match'. Below this is a 'Filter by Modality' section with a vertical scrollbar, listing the following categories and counts:

Modality	Count
Images	2317
Texts	2133
Videos	751
Audio	468

Datasets:

- ImageNet (1/2)

ImageNet Dataset | Papers With Code x Li, Wang - AI oceanography.pdf x +

https://paperswithcode.com/dataset/imagenet

Hotmail Academia LibGen Sci-Hub Patagonia Yahoo Nacion Trends Arqueomus AI Etnogeometria Giros Dialectics Otros favoritos

Search

Browse State-of-the-Art Datasets Methods More

Images

ImageNet

Edit

Introduced by Jia Deng et al. in [ImageNet: A large-scale hierarchical image database](#)

The **ImageNet** dataset contains 14,197,122 annotated images according to the WordNet hierarchy. Since 2010 the dataset is used in the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC), a benchmark in image classification and object detection. The publicly released dataset contains a set of manually annotated training images. A set of test images is also released, with the manual annotations withheld. ILSVRC annotations fall into one of two categories: (1) image-level annotation of a binary label for the presence or absence of an object class in the image, e.g., “there are cars in this image” but “there are no tigers,” and (2) object-level annotation of a tight bounding box and class label around an object instance in the image, e.g., “there is a screwdriver centered at position (20,25) with width of 50 pixels and height of 30 pixels”. The ImageNet project does not own the copyright of the images, therefore only thumbnails and URLs of images are provided.

- Total number of non-empty WordNet synsets: 21841
- Total number of images: 14197122
- Number of images with bounding box annotations: 1,034,908
- Number of synsets with SIFT features: 1000
- Number of images with SIFT features: 1.2 million

Source: <https://cs.stanford.edu/people/karpath...>

Usage

3k

Datasets

- ImageNet (2/2)

Search for a paper or author

Paper	Code	Results	Date	Stars ↑
MobileNets: Efficient Convolutional Neural Networks for Mobile Vision Applications	Code	Results	16 abr 2017	173.652
GIT: A Generative Image-to-text Transformer for Vision and Language	Code	Results	26 may 2022	95.606
TVLT: Textless Vision-Language Transformer	Code	—	27 sept 2022	95.606
AutoAugment: Learning Augmentation Policies from Data	Code	Results	23 may 2018	75.665
Density estimation using Real NVP	Code	Results	26 may 2016	75.665
Exploring the Limits of Language Modeling	Code	Results	6 feb 2016	75.665
A Simple Single-Scale Vision Transformer for Object Localization and Instance Segmentation	Code	—	16 dic 2021	75.665
Ensemble Adversarial Training: Attacks and Defenses	Code	—	18 may 2017	75.665
MorphNet: Fast & Simple Resource-Constrained Structure Learning of Deep Networks	Code	—	17 nov 2017	75.665
Progressive Neural Architecture Search	Code	Results	1 dic 2017	75.665

Showing 1 to 10 of 10,654 papers

Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 1066 Next

Datasets con impacto en estudio del Cambio Climático

- Dataset LIDAR – 2012 ([Surging Seas](#) – Climate Central)
- PapersWithCode Datasets (<https://paperswithcode.com/datasets>)
- SARCFMNet SAR Coastal Flooding Mapping Network
- SAR: Synthetic Aperture Radar
- Sentinel:
 - [ISPRS-Annals - SEN12MS – A CURATED DATASET OF GEOREFERENCED MULTI-SPECTRAL SENTINEL-1/2 IMAGERY FOR DEEP LEARNING AND DATA FUSION \(copernicus.org\)](#)
- BigEartNet v.1.0 :
 - <https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog>
- [Search for street view | Papers With Code](#)

Paper, Datasets y código para cambio climático

- https://paperswithcode.com/search?q_meta=&q_type=&q=climate

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL https://paperswithcode.com/search?q_meta=&q_type=&q=climate. The page features a search bar with the term "climate" and navigation links for "Browse State-of-the-Art", "Datasets", "Methods", and "More". A "Subscribe" button is visible in the top right corner.

The search results display two entries:

- Speed of technological transformations required in Europe to achieve different climate goals**
 - 4 code implementations • 20 Sep 2021
 - ★ 188
 - Buttons: Paper, Code
 - Category: Physics and Society
 - Abstract: Under the cost and performance assumptions applied, for a social cost of carbon (SCC) of 120EUR/tCO₂, transition paths under 1.5 and 1.6C budgets are, respectively, 8%, and 1% more expensive than the 2C-budget because building assets earlier costs more.
- Deep learning to represent sub-grid processes in climate models**
 - ★ 65

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the search bar with "Buscar", the system clock at 20:25 on 24/4/2023, and the language set to ESP.

Datasets para Cambio Climático

- <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?query=climate%20change&docid=L2cvMTFzeDMwM3lucA%3D%3D>

The screenshot shows a web browser window with multiple tabs. The active tab is 'Dataset Search' and the address bar contains the URL: <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?query=climate%20change&docid=L2cvMTFzeDMwM3lucA%3D%3D>. The search results page displays '100+ datasets found' and lists several results. The top result is 'Climate Change Data' from 'datacatalog.worldbank.org' and 'data.subak.org', updated on Apr 14, 2023. It provides links to explore the data at 'datacatalog.worldbank.org', 'Subak Data Catalogue | data...', and 'AmeriGEOSS Community Platfo...'. The dataset is provided by the 'World Bank' and has a 'public-licenses?fragment=cc' license. The description states: 'Data from World Development Indicators and Climate Change Knowledge Portal on climate systems, exposure to climate impacts, resilience, greenhouse gas emissions, and energy use.' Other results include 'Climate Change Data' from 'data.world' (updated Apr 14, 2023) and 'Twitter Climate Change Sentiment Dataset' from 'kaggle.com' (updated Nov 13, 2019). The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the time as 17:44 on 21/4/2023.

Dataset list - A list of the big... x | ISPRS-Annals - SEN12MS - A... x | BigEarthNet_IGARSS_2019.p... x | Climate change datasets | D... x | Dataset Search x

Google climate change

100+ datasets found

Climate Change Data
datacatalog.worldbank.org
data.subak.org
+1 more
databank, utf-8

Climate Change Data
data.world
csv, zip
Updated Apr 14, 2023

kaggle Twitter Climate Change Sentiment Dataset
kaggle.com
zip
Updated Nov 13, 2019

Climate Change Data

Explore at: datacatalog.worldbank.org [Subak Data Catalogue | data...](#) [AmeriGEOSS Community Platfo...](#)

utf-8, databank

Dataset provided by
World Bank

License
<https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/public-licenses?fragment=cc>

Description
Data from World Development Indicators and Climate Change Knowledge Portal on climate systems, exposure to climate impacts, resilience, greenhouse gas emissions, and energy use.

Buscar

17:44
21/4/2023

Datasets para Oceanografía

- <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?src=0&query=oceanography&docid=L2cvMTFqbnlfcjJmNQ%3D%3D>

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the Google Dataset Search interface. The search query is 'oceanography'. The results section shows '100+ datasets found'. The first result is 'NODC Standard Product: Oceanographic station profile...' with a red circular icon containing the letter 'C'. It lists sources like data.cnra.ca.gov and dev.gimi9.com, and is updated as of May 9, 2019. The second result is 'Meteorology, physical oceanography, transport of...' with a blue circular icon containing the letter 'D'. It lists sources like catalog.data.gov and search.dataone.org, and is updated as of Feb 26, 2021. The detailed view for this second result is expanded, showing the title 'Meteorology, physical oceanography, transport of water, biogeochemistry, and other parameters collected at fixed locations in the open ocean from the OceanSITES network'. Below the title, it says 'Explore at:' followed by five blue buttons with external links: catalog.data.gov, search.dataone.org, data.noaa.gov, accession.nodc.noaa.gov, and AmeriGEOSS Community Platfo... (truncated). Below the buttons, it lists 'Dataset updated' (Feb 26, 2021), 'Dataset provided by' (Point of Contact), 'Area covered' (Earth), and 'Description' (This collection comprises data covering meteorology, physical oceanography, transport of water, biogeochemistry, and parameters).

100+ datasets found

C NODC Standard Product: Oceanographic station profile...
data.cnra.ca.gov
dev.gimi9.com
+4more
html
Updated May 9, 2019

D Meteorology, physical oceanography, transport of...
catalog.data.gov
search.dataone.org
+4more
Updated Feb 26, 2021

Meteorology, physical oceanography, transport of water, biogeochemistry, and other parameters collected at fixed locations in the open ocean from the OceanSITES network

Explore at:

- catalog.data.gov
- search.dataone.org
- data.noaa.gov
- accession.nodc.noaa.gov
- AmeriGEOSS Community Platfo...
- data.wu.ac.at

Dataset updated
Feb 26, 2021

Dataset provided by
(Point of Contact)

Area covered
Earth

Description
This collection comprises data covering meteorology, physical oceanography, transport of water, biogeochemistry, and parameters

Datasets para Colombia

- <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?src=0&query=colombia&docid=L2cvMTFyYjM4OGg1Mw%3D%3D>

The screenshot shows a web browser window with a Google Dataset Search result. The search query is "Departamentos y municipios de Colombia". The results list 89 datasets found. The top result is "Departamentos y municipios de Colombia" from datos.gov.co and data.amerigeoss.org, updated on Mar 15, 2022. It is available in application/rdfxml +5 format. The second result is from kaggle.com, updated on Jan 8, 2021, in zip format. The third result is "Municipios por departamento" from datos.gov.co. The main view shows details for the first dataset, including links to explore it on "Datos Abiertos Colombia" and "AmeriGEOSS Community Platfo...", 216 scholarly articles citing it, and available formats: csv, json, application/rdfxml, tsv, xml, application/rssxml. The dataset was updated on Mar 15, 2022, authored by the Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística, and licensed under Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 (CC BY-SA 4.0). The area covered is Colombia.

89 datasets found

Departamentos y municipios de Colombia
datos.gov.co
data.amerigeoss.org
application/rdfxml +5
Updated Mar 15, 2022

Departamentos y municipios de colombia
kaggle.com
zip
Updated Jan 8, 2021

Municipios por departamento
datos.gov.co

Departamentos y municipios de Colombia

Explore at: [Datos Abiertos Colombia | d...](#) [AmeriGEOSS Community Platfo...](#)

216 scholarly articles cite this dataset ([View in Google Scholar](#))

csv, json, application/rdfxml, tsv, xml, application/rssxml

Dataset updated
Mar 15, 2022

Dataset authored and provided by
Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística

License
[Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 \(CC BY-SA 4.0\)](#)
License information was derived automatically

Area covered
Colombia

Datasets para Sentinel

- <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?src=0&query=sentinel&docid=L2cvMTFqbnlqdzFzOQ%3D%3D>

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying search results for 'sentinel' on the Google Dataset Search platform. The search bar at the top contains the query 'sentinel'. Below the search bar, there are filter buttons for 'Last updated', 'Download format', 'Usage rights', 'Topic', and 'Free'. A 'Saved datasets' button is also visible on the right. The search results show '100+ datasets found'. Three results are visible in the left sidebar:

- Sentinel-2** (registry.opendata.aws, data.subak.org) - Updated Apr 19, 2018
- Sentinel-2** (console.cloud.google.com) - Updated Feb 11, 2019
- Sentinel-2 MSI: MultiSpectral Instrument, Level-2A** (developers.google.com) - Updated Mar 28, 2017

The main content area displays details for the first result, 'Sentinel-2':

- Sentinel-2**
- Explore at: [registry.opendata.aws](#) and [Subak Data Catalogue | data...](#)
- 22 scholarly articles cite this dataset ([View in Google Scholar](#))
- Dataset updated**: Apr 19, 2018
- Dataset provided by**: [Sinergise](https://www.sinergise.com/)
- Description**: The [Sentinel-2 mission](#) is a land monitoring constellation of two satellites that provide high resolution optical imagery and provide continuity for the current SPOT and Landsat missions. The mission provides a global coverage of the Earth's land surface every 5 days, making the data of great use in on-going studies. L1C data are available from June 2015 globally. L2A data are available from November 2016 over Europe region and globally since January 2017.

The URL bar at the bottom shows <https://data.subak.org/dataset/sentinel-2>.

Sentinel1 y Sentinel 2

- [BigEarthNet - A Large-Scale Sentinel Benchmark Archive](https://www.datasetlist.com)

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://www.datasetlist.com>. The search bar contains the text 'sentinel'. The search results are displayed in a table with the following columns: NAME, YEAR, DESCRIPTION, LICENSE, and PAPER.

SEARCH	NAME	YEAR	DESCRIPTION	LICENSE	PAPER
sentinel	SEN12MS	2019	SEN12MS is a dataset consisting of 180,748 corresponding image triplets containing Sentinel-1 dual-pol SAR data, Sentinel-2 multi-spectral imagery, and MODIS-derived land cover maps.	CC BY 4.0	P
	BigEarthNet	2019	The BigEarthNet is a new large-scale Sentinel-2 benchmark archive, consisting of 590,326 Sentinel-2 image patches. To construct the BigEarthNet, 125 Sentinel-2 tiles acquired between June 2017 and May 2018 over the 10 countries (Austria, Belgium, Finland, Ireland, Kosovo, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Portugal, Serbia, Switzerland) of Europe were initially selected. All the tiles were atmospherically corrected by the Sentinel-2 Level 2A product generation and formatting tool (sen2cor). Then, they were divided into 590,326 non-overlapping image patches. Each image patch was annotated by the multiple land-cover classes (i.e., multi-labels) that were provided from the CORINE Land Cover database of the year 2018.	CDLA Permissive	P

On the left side of the page, there are filters for CATEGORY and LICENSE. The CATEGORY filter includes: All, Image, NLP, Self-driving, Question answering, Audio, and Medical. The LICENSE filter includes: All, Non-commercial, and Commercial.

Oceanografía (1/2)

- Xiaofeng Li & Fan Wang. *Artificial Intelligence Oceanography*. Springer, 2023.

Oceanografía (2/2)

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Forecasting Tropical Instability Waves Based on Artificial Intelligence	45
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MILA & Yoshua Bengio

- Montréal Institute for Learning Algorithms

CORE ACADEMIC MEMBER

YOSHUA BENGIO

Scientific Director, Mila & IVADO,
Full Professor, Samsung AI
Professor, Université de Montréal,
Canada CIFAR AI Chair

Yoshua Bengio

Demo

- <https://ThisClimateDoesNotExist.com>
- Yoshua Bengio y equipo [Mila](#) de la Universidad de Montréal
- Efecto de inundación, fuego y polución atmosférica sobre imágenes de Street View
 - Efecto de inundación en mi propia casa
 - Idem en Universidad de La Guajira

Trabajos de Yoshua Bengio & MILA (1/3)

- <https://mila.quebec/en/publications/?q=Climate%20Change>

2021-10

ClimateGAN: Raising Climate Change Awareness by Generating Images of Floods

Victor Schmidt, Alexandra Sasha Luccioni, Mélisande Teng, Tianyu Zhang, Alexia Reynaud, Sunand Raghupathi, Gautier Cosne, Adrien Juraver, Vahe Vardanyan, Alex Hernandez-Garcia and Yoshua Bengio

effects of global warming, climate change, action, flooding, environmental resource management, task, architecture, computer science, raising, domain adaptation

[arXiv preprint arXiv:2110.02871](#) (2021-10-06) [dblp.uni-trier.de](#) [PDF](#)

2021-01

Using Artificial Intelligence to Visualize the Impacts of Climate Change

Alexandra Luccioni, Victor Schmidt, Vahe Vardanyan, Yoshua Bengio and Theresa-Marie Rhyne

effects of global warming, climate change, extreme weather, data visualization, user experience design, visualization, process, scale, natural environment, computer science, artificial intelligence

[IEEE Computer Graphics and Applications](#) (2021-01-01) [ieeexplore.ieee.org](#)

2020-12

Spatiotemporal Features Improve Fine-Grained Butterfly Image Classification

Marta Skreta, Sasha Luccioni and David Rolnick

contextual image classification, butterfly, pattern recognition, computer science, artificial intelligence

[NeurIPS 2020 Workshop on Tackling Climate Change with Machine Learning](#) (2020-12-11) [www.climatechange.ai](#) [PDF](#)

Trabajos de Yoshua Bengio & MILA (2/3)

Publications - Mila x +
https://mila.quebec/en/publications/?q=Climate%20Change
Hotmail Academia LibGen Sci-Hub Patagonia Yahoo Nacion Trends Arqueomus AI Etnogeometria Giros Dialectics Otros favoritos

Machine Learning for Glacier Monitoring in the Hindu Kush Himalaya.

Shimaa Baraka, Benjamin Akera, Bibek Aryal, Tenzing Sherpa, Finu Shresta, Anthony Ortiz, Kris Sankaran, Juan M. Lavista Ferres, Mir Matin and Yoshua Bengio

glacier, climate change, satellite imagery, remote sensing, satellite, process, machine learning, geology, artificial intelligence, ecological monitoring, hindu kush

NeurIPS CCAI (2020-12-08) www.microsoft.com [LATEST on arXiv preprint arXiv:2012.05013 (2020-12-09)]

Establishing an evaluation metric to quantify climate change image realism

Sharon Zhou, Alexandra Luccioni, Gautier Cosne, Michael S Bernstein and Yoshua Bengio

generative model, machine learning, generative grammar, computer science, classifier, realism, public interest, climate change, artificial intelligence

Informatica : Journal of Applied Machines Electrical Electronics Computer Science and Communication Systems (2020-12-01) digitalintelligentsiaconsultancyservices.com [Also on Machine Learning: Science and Technology (2020-04-09)] [Also on arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.10143 (2019-10-22)]

2020-01

Using Simulated Data to Generate Images of Climate Change

Gautier Cosne, Adrien Juraver, Mélisande Teng, Victor Schmidt, Vahe Vardanyan, Alexandra Luccioni and Yoshua Bengio

usability, simulated data, machine learning, generative grammar, data access, computer science, climate change, artificial intelligence, architecture, adversarial system, a domain

arXiv preprint arXiv:2001.09531 (2020-01-26) ui.adsabs.harvard.edu PDF

2019-10

Predicting ice flow using machine learning.

Yimeng Min, S. Karthik Mukkavilli and Yoshua Bengio

unsupervised learning, optical flow, machine learning, ice stream, global temperature, glacier, cryosphere, computer science, cloud cover, climate change, artificial intelligence

Trabajos de Yoshua Bengio & MILA (3/3)

2019-08

Digital Democracy Project: Research memo #2 - climate change

Taylor Owen, Peter Loewen, Derek Ruths, Aengus Bridgman, Meghan Keenan, Stephanie MacLellan, Eric Merkley, Andrew Potter, Beata Skazinetsky and Oleg Zhilin

democracy, climate change, political economy, political science

(venue unknown) (2019-08-30) apo.org.au

2019-06

Tackling Climate Change with Machine Learning

David Rolnick, Priya L. Donti, Lynn H. Kaack, Kelly Kochanski, Alexandre Lacoste, Kris Sankaran, Andrew Slavin Ross, Nikola Milojevic-Dupont, Natasha Jaques, Anna Waldman-Brown, Alexandra Luccioni, Tegan Maharaj, Evan D. Sherwin, S. Karthik Mukkavilli, Konrad P. Kording, Carla P. Gomes, Andrew Y. Ng, Demis Hassabis, John C. Platt, Felix Creutzig... (2 more)

emergency management, climate change, greenhouse gas, smart grid, computer science, humanity, machine learning, artificial intelligence

arXiv preprint [arXiv:1906.05433](https://arxiv.org/abs/1906.05433) (2019-06-10) ui.adsabs.harvard.edu PDF

2019-05

Visualizing the Consequences of Climate Change Using Cycle-Consistent Adversarial Networks

Victor Schmidt, Alexandra Luccioni, S. Karthik Mukkavilli, Narmada Balasooriya, Kris Sankaran, Jennifer Chayes and Yoshua Bengio

extreme weather, environmental resource management, effects of global warming, credibility, computer science, climate model, climate change, adversarial system

arXiv preprint [arXiv:1905.03709](https://arxiv.org/abs/1905.03709) (2019-05-02) ui.adsabs.harvard.edu PDF

Climate Demo 1

- <https://ThisClimateDoesNotExist.com>

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the address bar containing <https://thisclimatedoesnotexist.com/home>. The website header includes the logo and navigation links: "Visualize climate change", "What now?", "About", and "FR". The main content area features the text "These images are generated by artificial intelligence (AI)" next to a photograph of St. Basil's Cathedral. Below this, the text "But the environmental disasters they portray are very real" is displayed next to a photograph of a building that appears to be partially submerged in water.

Can you imagine these kinds of disasters happening in your own backyard?

Climate Demo 2

[This Climate Does Not Exist](#) Visualize climate change What now? About FR

Climate change does not impact everyone equally. For the planet to tackle the climate crisis, we all need to act as though our homes were directly affected.

We have harnessed AI to build a tool that lets you imagine the impact of the climate crisis we face, one address at a time.

[START](#)

Climate Demo 3

[Visualize climate change](#)

[What now?](#)

[About](#)

[FR](#)

- [Introduction](#)
- [Address](#)
- [Environmental Impacts](#)
- [Learn more...](#)
- [Your visualization is processing...](#)

A Window On the Global Crisis

Perhaps you have experienced the odd heatwave or the occasional spring flood, but some of us live through these extreme weather events all too often. That is because climate change does not affect everyone at the same time or on the same scale. It takes different forms depending on where we live.

All over the world, people are losing their homes to wildfires and being impacted by floods, as well as suffering the effects of air pollution on their health.

Climate Demo 4

[Visualize climate change](#)

[What now?](#)

[About](#)

[FR](#)

forms depending on where we live.

All over the world, people are losing their homes to wildfires and being impacted by floods, as well as suffering the effects of air pollution on their health.

The following experience provides a window into the far-reaching ways climate change affects the lives of millions of people worldwide, except that this window overlooks your street and the places you hold dear.

Pick a location

Search for any address listed on Google Street View. Here are a few ideas to guide you:

- Your current home
- Your childhood home

Climate Demo 5

This Climate Does Not Exist

[Visualize climate change](#)

[What now?](#)

[About](#)

[FR](#)

○ Your favorite restaurant

Type in an address

Climate Demo 6

(3) Carlos Reynoso | Universidad x ThisClimateDoesNotExist.com x +

https://thisclimatedoesnotexist.com/visualize

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This Climate Does Not Exist Visualize climate change What now? About FR

○ Your favorite restaurant

Solis 215

- Solís 215 Buenos Aires, Argentina
- 215 Solis Street Tondo, Manila, Gran Manila, Fili...
- Solís 215 Provincia de Buenos Aires, Argentina
- Manuel Jiménez Solis 215 Insurgentes de Valla...
- Solís 215 Mar de Ajó, Provincia de Buenos Aires...

powered by Google

Datos de mapas ©2023 Términos de uso

Climate Demo 7

(3) Carlos Reynoso | Universidad x ThisClimateDoesNotExist.com x +

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This Climate Does Not Exist Visualize climate change What now? About FR

Your favorite restaurant

Solís 215, C1078AAE CABA, Arg

Solís 215, C1078AAE CABA, Argentina

LAUNCH THE VISUALIZATION

Climate Demo 8

[Visualize climate change](#)

[What now?](#)

[About](#)

[FR](#)

[Introduction](#)

[Solís 215, C1078AAE
CABA, Argentina](#)

[Environmental
Impacts](#)

[Learn more...](#)

[Your visualization is
ready.](#)

Select an Impact

When you have a fever, your body temperature rises above the normal range by one or two degrees, causing you to feel unwell, signaling that something is wrong in your body. Planet Earth is even more sensitive to temperature increases. Since the pre-industrial period, global average temperatures have risen by 1.25°C, with the last 10 years being the hottest ever recorded. Much like your body, which sends clear physical signals when you are sick, our planet's lands, oceans and atmosphere also react to climate change.

Among these "symptoms," we see an intensification in frequency and scale of extreme weather events such as floods and forest fires, along with a deterioration in air quality caused by human activity and the burning of

Climate Demo 9

[Visualize climate change](#)

[What now?](#)

[About](#)

[FR](#)

[Introduction](#)

[Solís 215, C1078AAE
CABA, Argentina](#)

[Try another address](#)

[Environmental
Impacts](#)

[Learn more...](#)

[Your visualization is
ready.](#)

Here is some information on climate change impacts for you to read while we generate your image. This may take a few seconds.

Scroll

Scroll

Flood

Climate Demo 10

[Visualize climate change](#)

[What now?](#)

[About](#)

[FR](#)

Flooding is often the result of heavy rainfall, rapid melting of snow or ice, or storms in coastal areas. All these phenomena have increased with climate change, in terms of both frequency and intensity.

The Human Toll

Flash floods kill
5000
people per year

Sea levels are expected to rise by
2 metres
by the end of the century

Rising sea levels could disrupt the lives of

1 billion
people by the end of 2050.

Introduction

Solís 215, C1078AAE
CABA, Argentina

Try another address

Environmental Impacts

Learn more...

Your visualization is ready.

Climate Demo 11

(3) Carlos Reynoso | Universidad x ThisClimateDoesNotExist.com x +

https://thisclimatedoesnotexist.com/visualize

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 This Climate Does Not Exist

[Visualize climate change](#) [What now?](#) [About](#) [FR](#)

Your visualization is ready! [Scroll](#)

- Introduction
- Solís 215, C1078AAE
CABA, Argentina
- Try another address
- Environmental Impacts
- Learn more...
- Your visualization is ready.

Your visualization

I wish to make the address of the current visualization visible in the link I am sharing.

While it is impossible at this time to predict when or whether this phenomenon could affect this location, we should all be concerned about the high probability of

Climate Demo 12

https://thisclimatedoesnotexist.com/visualize

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This Climate Does Not Exist

[Visualize climate change](#) [What now?](#) [About](#) [FR](#)

[f](#) [t](#) [in](#) [link](#) [email](#)

I wish to make the address of the current visualization visible in the link I am sharing.

Introduction
Solís 215, C1078AAE
CABA, Argentina

Try another address

Environmental Impacts

Learn more...

Your visualization

Flood
Wildfire
Smog

While it is impossible at this time to predict when or whether this phenomenon could affect this location, we should all be concerned about the high probability of it happening to thousands or millions of people around the world.

Human activity has the greatest impact on current rates of global heating. Click on "What now?" to find out what you can do about it.

Climate Demo 13

[Visualize climate change](#) [What now?](#) [About](#) [FR](#)

YOUR VISUALIZATION

I wish to make the address of the current visualization visible in the link I am sharing.

While it is impossible at this time to predict when or whether this phenomenon could affect this location, we should all be concerned about the high probability of it happening to thousands or millions of people around the world.

Human activity has the greatest impact on current rates of global heating. Click on "What now?" to find out what you can do about it.

[Introduction](#)

Solís 215, C1078AAE
CABA, Argentina

[Try another address](#)

[Environmental Impacts](#)

[Learn more...](#)

Your visualization

Flood

Wildfire

Smog

Climate Demo 14

[Visualize climate change](#)

[What now?](#)

[About](#)

[FR](#)

○ Your favorite restaurant

Cra. 6 &, Cl. 1, Riohacha, La Guajira, Colombia

Cra. 6 &, Cl. 1, Riohacha, La Guajira, Colombia

**LAUNCH THE
VISUALIZATION**

Climate Demo 15

[Visualize climate change](#) [What now?](#) [About](#) [FR](#)

I wish to make the address of the current visualization visible in the link I am sharing.

While it is impossible at this time to predict when or whether this phenomenon could affect this location, we should all be concerned about the high probability of it happening to thousands or millions of people around the world.

Human activity has the greatest impact on current rates of global heating. Click on "What now?" to find out what you can do about it.

- Introduction
- Cra. 6 &, Cl. 1, Riohacha, La Guajira, Colombia
- Try another address
- Environmental Impacts
- Learn more...
- Your visualization
 - Flood
 - Wildfire
 - Smog

Climate Demo 16

(3) Carlos Reynoso | Universidad x ThisClimateDoesNotExist.com x +

https://thisclimatedoesnotexist.com/visualize

Hotmail Academia LibGen Sci-Hub Patagonia Yahoo Nacion Trends Arqueomus AI Etnogeometria Giros Dialectics Otros favoritos

This Climate Does Not Exist [Visualize climate change](#) [What now?](#) [About](#) [FR](#)

I wish to make the address of the current visualization visible in the link I am sharing.

Introduction
Cra. 6 &, Cl. 1, Riohacha, La Guajira, Colombia
[Try another address](#)
Environmental Impacts
[Learn more...](#)
Your visualization
[Flood](#)
[Wildfire](#)
[Smog](#)

While it is impossible at this time to predict when or whether this phenomenon could affect this location, we should all be concerned about the high probability of it happening to thousands or millions of people around the world.

Human activity has the greatest impact on current rates of global heating. Click on "What now?" to find out what you can do about it.

Documentación técnica en el sitio

- [Establishing an evaluation metric to quantify climate change image realism \(iop.org\)](https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/2632-2153/ab7657/pdf)

MACHINE
LEARNING
Science and Technology

PAPER

Establishing an evaluation metric to quantify climate change image realism*

OPEN ACCESS

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³ Equal contribution.

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Keywords: deep learning, generative adversarial networks, climate change, generative network evaluation, domain transfer

Abstract

Riohacha a Cabo de la Vela

- [Climate Central | Land below 3.0 meters of water](https://coastal.climatecentral.org/map/10/-72.4554/11.8703/?theme=water_level&map_type=water_level_above_m...)

Climate Central- Surging seas

- [Science Behind the Tool | Surging Seas: Sea level rise analysis by Climate Central](https://sealevel.climatecentral.org/maps/science-behind-the-tool/) – Red neuronal MLP* – Dataset LiDAR (2012)

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://sealevel.climatecentral.org/maps/science-behind-the-tool/>. The page title is "Surging Seas" and the subtitle is "Sea level rise analysis by CLIMATE CENTRAL". The navigation menu includes "About", "Maps & Tools", "Research", "Basics", "Responses", and "News".

Science Behind the Tool

Click on a quick link below to learn more about the science behind our tools:

[Risk Zone Map](#) | [Risk Finder](#) | [Mapping Choices](#)

Risk Zone Map

The research behind the [Risk Zone Map](#) is based on [peer-reviewed science](#). That 2012 analysis used the best available national coverage elevation dataset at the time. Risk Zone Map now uses far more accurate laser-based (LiDAR) elevation data.

Risk Finder

The research behind the Surging Seas [Risk Finder](#) is based on peer-reviewed science. [One core study](#), published in 2012, projects local sea level rise and coastal flood risk; [the other study](#) (same year) maps and assesses exposure to sea level rise. Risk Finder improves on both studies by adding updated sea level projections and data.

Updated Mapping and Exposure Analysis

- **Improved elevation data:** Our 2012 analysis used the best available national coverage elevation dataset at the time. This analysis uses a far more accurate, laser-based (LiDAR) elevation data.

***MLP: Multi Layer Perceptron**

GANs en la Web

Con énfasis en cambio climático

- [18 Impressive Applications of Generative Adversarial Networks \(GANs\) - MachineLearningMastery.com](#)
- [AI can show us the ravages of climate change | MIT Technology Review](#)
- [Artificial intelligence for Climate Change, Biodiversity and Earth System Models \(amitray.com\)](#)
- [Climate change: Floods, fires, smog: AI delivers images of how climate change could affect your city | U.S. | EL PAÍS English \(elpais.com\)](#)
- [Climate simulation more realistic with Artificial Intelligence | PreventionWeb](#)
- [GANs for Dynamic Spatio-Temporal Patterns | Climate Change AI](#)
- [Generative Adversarial Networks for Climate Change Scenarios \(urbanai.fr\)](#)
- [Generative-adversarial-network · GitHub Topics · GitHub](#)
- [Projecting Climate Change Into Photos With Generative Adversarial Networks - Unite.AI](#)

Recursos

- [Página](#) del autor dedicada en Academia.edu

Redes generativas adversarias en tiempos de posverdad: Avances, falacias, promesas y amenazas en torno del cambio climático y el calentamiento global (2023)

Carlos Reynoso

2023, Conferencia de Inteligencia Artificial para el II Congreso Internacional de Gestión Integral frente al Cambio Climático en la Universidad de La Guajira, mayo de 2023. Actualización del 4 de abril

Primeros 3% 208 Visualizaciones 31 Páginas 11 Archivos

Machine Learning, Connectionism, Artificial Neural Networks, Cambio climático, Deep Learning ... más

Mostrar más

Tras más de treinta años sopesando los logros y las contrariedades de la Inteligencia Artificial desde mi primera disertación de doctorado (disponible en https://www.academia.edu/53296238/Antropolog%C3%ADa_y_programaci%C3%B3n_l%C3%B3gica_... más información

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PDF Original Resumen Relacionado

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Carlos Reynoso Universidad de Buenos Aires Faculty Member

Doctor en Antropología Social por la Universidad Nacional de Misiones, Argentina. Doctor Honoris Causa por la Universidad del Altiplano en Puno, Perú. Ex-Profesor de Elementos de Lingüística y Semiótica, de Teorías Antropológicas Contemporáneas, de A ... more

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